

HOW TO IMPROVE SPEAKING WITHOUT A PARTNER

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Annotation: There are a lot of great ways to improve your (English) speaking skills by yourself. You can watch movies and TV shows and shadow the speech of the native actors. Or, practice singing songs aloud in your target language. Another option is to read aloud and record yourself so you can self-assess your fluency and accent. In this article, we will look at how to improve your speaking without assistance.

Keywords: speaking skills, language, target language, source language, fluency, assistance, native speakers, practice, shadowing, speech.

Аннотация: Существует множество отличных способов улучшить свои (английские) разговорные навыки самостоятельно. Вы можете смотреть фильмы и телепередачи и копировать речь актеров-носителей языка. Или практиковаться в пении песен вслух на вашем целевом языке. Другой вариант — читать вслух и записывать себя, чтобы вы могли самостоятельно оценить свою беглость и акцент. В этой статье мы рассмотрим, как улучшить свою речь без посторонней помощи.

Ключевые слова: разговорные навыки, язык, целевой язык, исходный язык, беглость, помощь, носители языка, практика, копирование, речь

Annotatsiya: O'zingizning (ingliz tilida) so'zlashuv ko'nikmalingizni oshirishning ko'plab ajoyib usullari mavjud. Siz filmlar va teleko'rsatuvlarni tomosha qilishingiz va mahalliy aktyorlarning nutqiga soya solishingiz mumkin. Yoki o'z tilingizda baland ovozda qo'shiq kuylashni mashq qiling. Yana bir variant - ovoz chiqarib o'qing va o'zingizni yozib oling, shunda siz o'zingizning ravonligingiz va urg'ungizni o'zingiz baholaysiz. Ushbu maqolada biz yordamisiz nutqingizni qanday yaxshilashni ko'rib chiqamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: nutq qobiliyatlari, til, maqsadli til, manba tili, ravonlik, yordam, ona tilida so'zlashuvchilar, amaliyot, soya, nutq.

INTRODUCTION

In today's fast-paced and technological world, people from different backgrounds, ethnicities and languages are interacting now more than ever before. What used to take weeks to communicate via letter can now be accomplished in mere minutes through a text message. This means if you want to keep up with the world today, learning another language could be a great first step. Not only can learning a second language have a multitude of personal benefits in your life, but it can also have a profound impact on your relationships with the people around you.

People who know how to talk in English can relate to people from other countries across the world[1]. English is spoken by a wide variety of people across the globe. Speaking in English can help a person to broaden their world starting from getting admission to good colleges and universities abroad to job opportunities. Learning English can help people to improve their quality of life. They can think about pursuing an international career and making a name for themselves in countries other than India. Many online spoken English classes offer classes to Beginners, Intermediate, and Advanced learners[4]. The lessons are designed by qualified

English tutors based on the understanding capacity and learning ability of the students. Looking for online spoken English tips & tricks that you can follow yourself without any partner.

If you are practicing by yourself, you can try choosing random topics and practice giving a speech in front of a mirror. You can also try to record and listen to your speech. For more dynamic conversation, you can use some apps that will connect you to native speakers with whom you can converse depending on your free time. Here are a few recommendations:

- iTalki: Here you can offer other users help to practice speaking in your language, and get help from native English speakers.
- Busuu: You can not only connect with native speakers, but you will also find different tasks and activities to practice.
- Lingoglobe: You can see which users are online and connect with them to practice. You can find users who share similar interests and hobbies as you.
- HelloTalk: You can converse with native speakers or just share short voice messages/audio files.

You can also try joining a spoken English class which might help you with staying focused as you go through your learning journey. The DoubtNut app, for example, offers one at a very affordable price. Most importantly, remember that becoming fluent in speaking is a marathon, not a sprint, so you will need to keep practicing regularly[5].

Reasons to learn how to converse in English

- English is a global language
- Knowing how to talk in English can help people get a job in the global market
- People knowing how to talk in English can easily mingle with people from other countries
- English is an important language in the media industry
- It is the language of the Internet which is a powerhouse of information
- Travelling abroad becomes easier for people who speak English well.
- It is an important language for business
- Getting admission to abroad colleges gets easier with knowledge of English
- English offers access to multiple cultures

It might seem to be joking, but I believe watching television is not only entertaining, it can also be very educational. From now on, whenever you watch television, try to listen to the words that the actors and actresses are saying and also try to listen to the accent they are using. You can also watch any of your favourite sports, but the commentary should be in English[6]. These will help you to follow the pronunciation and accent of a particular word.

To read the dialogue even if you are unable to comprehend what the performers are saying, you can also choose to leave the subtitles on. You can Google a word or ask someone if you're stuck or don't know what it means. This will make sense to you when hearing what is being said. This exercise will also assist you in comprehending the structure of English sentences. Pay attention to the sentence structure. It will support you in writing and speaking English. Reading can also help you become more fluent in spoken English. Everything that is in front of you should be read, including storybooks, magazines, and newspapers. Read anything you want to read, but make time to read every day. Reading can greatly improve your language fluency. You should read tale books, in my opinion, since they will keep you interested in the characters[2]. Many new words may appear while you read, some of which you may not be familiar with. Carry a notebook with you and make a note of any new words you come across.

So that when you've finished reading, you can verify their meaning. This is a very effective way to learn spoken English without a partner, in this method you have to close the door of your room and start speaking in front of the mirror. Speak whatever you want but speak, there are many cases in which people get scared from speaking and they don't speak. At first, you will speak the wrong English and it is normal for new spoken English learners. If you speak in a closed room in front of a mirror, then you can come across your mistakes easily and the plus point is there is nobody to judge you or to laugh at you. In this way, you cannot improve your basic spoken English skills. You can also learn some new words, and follow the same procedure and if you can't understand the meaning of a particular word then after speaking you can go through the meaning of those new words. This will also improve your stock of words and vocabulary in the process of improving spoken English fluency[7].

As we discussed, earlier reading English is very essential and you have to follow that while you read English, try to read it loudly so that you can hear your voice. Reading loudly will also help you to enhance your pronunciation and this will clear your speaking ability[3]. Read anything daily for at least 10 minutes, you can also exercise the below-mentioned tips to make your grip more efficient in spoken English:

- In a real conversation, you can find it difficult to use some terms appropriately or perhaps hesitant to use them at all if you haven't used them much. Reading aloud from a newspaper, magazine, or other text will compel you to use a wide variety of words regularly (keep in mind that these sources have a far larger vocabulary than you do, so you'll be exposed to the sounds of many new words). This will help you become accustomed to their sounds and increase the likelihood that you'll use them in a genuine conversation.
- Because these words will continue to come up in the future, reading aloud will help you retain the pronunciation you're learning from online dictionaries (discussed in the preceding paragraph).
- Finally, you can utilise this exercise to practise your pace, emphasis pauses, and intonation—all of which were discussed previously in the essay[8].

CONCLUSION

The best way to improve your spoken English is to keep practising it. The more you speak, the more you will understand the words and, ultimately, the language itself. You can achieve fluency in English, pick any book or newspaper of your choice and start reading. Find a native speaker if feasible, it will help to learn English with more efficiency. If you think that it will be difficult for you to learn spoken English alone, you should connect with FastInfo Class®. We have a pool of good and experienced teachers. Many of the FastInfo Classes' students are working with top MNCs. Many of the students of FastInfo Class® are working with top MNCs.

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